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MODERN VECTOR OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS REHABILITATION

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The search for ways to preserve and develop the nation, its health, labour and reproductive sufficiency should be addressed to pedagogical community, which is increasingly getting aware of its responsibility for physical, social and psychological well-being of future generations [10, 11]. Significant reserve in this regard is seen in physical culture and sports rehabilitation, i.e. the system of activities developed by means of physical exercises to restore a person's health and those physical culture and sports aimed at recovery and compensation of functional body capabilities, as well as improving person's physical and psychological condition – as stated in the Law of Ukraine “On Physical Culture and Sports”, Article 1 [3].

The Decree of the President of Ukraine as of August 24, 2020 № 342 “Issues of Development of National System of Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation for War Veterans and Their Family Members, Families of Deceased War Veterans” has approved the “National Strategy for Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation for War Veterans and Their Family Members, Families of Deceased War Veterans”. The purpose of this strategy is to create conditions for the formation and further development of a national system of physical culture and sports rehabilitation for war veterans and their family members, families of deceased war veterans [8].

Progress of science and technology, socio-economic and cultural changes in society actualize the task of training highly qualified and competitive specialists in physical culture and sports rehabilitation, given that the search for optimal ways to train highly qualified specialists that will have a sufficient level of competitiveness in the labour market has turned out to be one of the most significant issues for contemporary higher education [4].

Over the past twenty years the staff of the Department of Kinesiology and Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation of the National University of Ukraine on Physical Education and Sport (NUUPES) has accumulated a significant amount of scientific knowledge (with 3 doctoral and 20 PhD theses defended), four textbooks prepared, more than ten monographs published; the latter consider the restoration of human motor function, the functional capabilities of human body aimed at improving physical condition at different stages of ontogenesis by means of physical culture and sports [4].

At NUUPES starting from 2020 academic year a specialization/major “Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation” (field of knowledge: 01 Education / Pedagogy) has been launched within the first (Bachelor's) degree of higher education – educational and professional program in the specialty 017 Physical Culture and Sports; as well as a specialization/major “Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation” (field of knowledge: 01 Education / Pedagogy) has been launched within the second (Master's) degree of higher education – educational and professional program in the specialty 017 Physical Culture and Sports.

Given the above, special importance is given to scientific developments related to:

- ✓ development of theoretical schemes and models for organizing and conducting research in the field of physical culture and sports rehabilitation;
- ✓ screening-assessment of individual's motor skills and development of technologies for improvement of their physical qualities;
- ✓ arrangement of monitoring for the state of human body spatial organization and health state of various socio-demographic and age groups;
- ✓ determining individual peculiarities of human psychomotor skills;
- ✓ diagnostics of the state of person's musculoskeletal system (MSS), development of modern technologies and means for recovering from these disorders;
- ✓ development of innovative technologies of adaptive physical recreation;
- ✓ substantiation of organizational and pedagogical conditions for the development of physical culture and sports rehabilitation in megacities and other territorial communities;
- ✓ design of recreational, health-enhancing and health-forming technologies for different population groups;
- ✓ designing preventive measures in the field of physical culture and sports rehabilitation;
- ✓ development of innovative technologies for social adaptation and improving the physical condition of persons with disabilities;
- ✓ design of information and communication technologies in practical and scientific activities in the field of physical culture and sports rehabilitation;
- ✓ development of technologies of physical culture and sports rehabilitation for elderly people;
- ✓ development of technologies aimed at solving problems of ergonomics in physical culture and sports rehabilitation;
- ✓ analysis of needs, values, motivation for having a healthy lifestyle among people with disabilities, determining their compliance with the current stage of social development, humanistic ideals of world culture, search for effective ways to form the foundations of a healthy lifestyle for the above contingent;
- ✓ development of technologies for mastering motor activities by people with health issues (including people with disabilities) that allow them to implement vital and professionally important skills, recreation and switching from basic household and professional activities, health effects on the human body, extreme and creative types of health-improving motor activity;
- ✓ development of technologies for recovery and prevention of human body dysfunction by means of physical culture and sports rehabilitation targeting war veterans and their family members, families of deceased war veterans; this is implemented through timeliness, continuity and complexity of rehabilitation measures;
- ✓ development of technologies for effective restoration of physical, psychological and social functions of war veterans for their further return to military service or their social and labour adaptation by means of physical culture and sports rehabilitation, implementation of measures to rehabilitate veterans' families, families of deceased war veterans;
- ✓ development of approaches aimed at involving war veterans and their family members, families of deceased war veterans in physical culture and sports rehabilitation, resocialization, gaining new knowledge and competencies to ensure their economic independence, transforming a healthy lifestyle into everyday practice [4].

Obviously, scientific research in which physical culture and sports rehabilitation is seen from the point of view of understanding the person's bio-sociocultural essence can be of a fundamental nature. This allows us to combine different views into a systematically constructed

concept that characterize its essential characteristics in substantive, structural, functional, value and activity aspects, achieving a deeper socio-cultural understanding of its integrative, spiritual and physical essence [5, 6, 9].

As an example, below are a number of scientific developments made recently at the Department of Kinesiology and Physical Culture and Sports Rehabilitation of NUUPES.

The methodological basis of N.M. Honcharova's research [1, 2] has been the dialectical laws of social phenomena and processes development, consideration of physical education process as part of a higher order – a healthy lifestyle – and adaptation of accumulated knowledge to the real conditions of Ukraine in modern historical stage of its development, as well as philosophical views on humanism – a system of views on human as the highest value, characterized by the following features, namely respect for freedom and dignity of every person; taking into account the interests, needs and individual characteristics of each person; human well-being; providing people with equal opportunities for personal development and self-improvement; high moral relations among people.

Thorough analysis of scientific and methodological literature and current trends in the development of practical activities for the formation of children's health has become the basis for substantiation and development of the author's concept of health technologies applied in the process of physical education for primary school children [1, 2]. In the process of concept substantiation, the specialist [1, 2] has identified three vectors of scientific thought – the prerequisites for the concept development (social, biological, personal). The functioning of the proposed concept has been considered through the definition of conceptual approaches (systemic, synergetic, activity, dialectical, personality-oriented, differentiated, axiological, participatory, sociocultural, competence, environmental, integrative), conceptual foundations (goals, objectives, implementation methods, methods, methods). The components of the developed concept have been health-forming technologies for primary school children, which were integrated into the structure of the physical education process for primary school children [1, 2].

The practical implementation of the developed concept is contained in health-promoting technologies, the content of which has been determined in accordance with the approaches to the basic stages of planning health-promoting activities. The proposed technologies are implemented in three successive stages: adaptive-preparatory, main, final [1, 2]. The functioning of technology has been determined by the key provisions that defined the areas of activity in accordance with the characteristics of the primary school children's body and areas of children's health formation in the process of physical education. The programs of classes within the implementation of technologies have consisted of five components, including adaptive, epistemological, axiological, operational-activity, control ones [1, 2]. The implementation of the developed concept has been considered on the example of the predominant use of active tourism. Means of active tourism in the process of physical education of primary school children have significant health potential for children, the formation of values in health, experience of social interaction in the tourist group [1, 2].

Methodology of scientific research by N. L. Nosova [7] has been determined by the transformation of an array of theoretical and empirical knowledge about the process of rehabilitation for children with functional disorders (muscular-skeletal system), its algorithmization at a high level of functioning, integrity from the standpoint of theoretical principles and practice unity.

The specialist [7] has developed a concept of preventive physical rehabilitation of preschool children with functional disorders of muscular-skeletal system, which is based on modern

methodological approaches and aims to improve the functional state of its structure. The components of the concept include prerequisites (biological, clinical, social, personal, methodological), purpose, objectives, principles, conditions of its implementation; diagnostic vector with its components (axiological, diagnostic, correctional and prophylactic) and rehabilitation vector, which includes correctional and prophylactic and criterion-evaluation components [7]. The axiological component is aimed at forming a valuable attitude to health in general and posture in particular among preschool children and their parents. The diagnostic component includes a computer software "Habitus", which allows screening of the biogeometric posture profile and analytical methods to determine the biostatic body parameters [7]. The information and methodological component provides parents and educators with information on the term "posture" and types of its disorders, provides physical rehabilitation specialists with guidelines for assessing the level of biogeometric posture profile among 5-6 year-old children, acquaints with the specifics of modern methods and control tools, prevention and correction of posture disorders, allows creating an individual information database by coping information from medical cards with the help of "Posture control database 1.0" software, track the date of the next medical examination, monitor the dynamics of posture and support-spring properties of the foot and compare them with the results of medical examination. Corrective and prophylactic component is aimed at correcting existing functional disorders of muscular-skeletal system among preschool children and prevention of its static deformities. The criterion-evaluation component allows to characterize the indicators of the functional state of the muscular-skeletal system, support-spring properties of the foot, coordination abilities, biostatic indicators of the body and life quality among preschool children in the long run [7].

Keywords: physical culture and sports rehabilitation, methodology, concept.

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